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Media Type Availability and Usage in the Development of Rural Communities In Southeast, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study, media type availability and usage in the development of rural communities in Southeast Nigeria, was carried out to investigate the availability of various media among rural dwellers of Southeast Nigeria for development purposes. Also to ascertain the accessibility of media type and to identify the challenges of the various media in the select communities, find out the media used by government for promoting rural development and finally to ascertain the effectiveness of the media used by government in achieving development purposes. The study was anchored on Technological Determinism and Participatory theories. The researcher adopted a combined use of survey and indepth interview, to get answers to the research questions. For the purpose of the study, three states in Southeast Nigeria, namely, Anambra, Ebonyi and Enugu States were select out of the five states that make up the southeast zone. Eighteen communities each were purposively selected from the three states. The population of the 18 communities is 546,906. Out of this population, a sample size of 384 was select using Krejcie and Morgan table of sample size determination. Indepth interview were conducted on government officials. The responses were analysed thematically using the explanation building technique. Findings show that indigenous media, or a media and radio are the most effective channel of communication to the rural communities for effective participation and sustainability of development projects conclusion of the research is that the government has not utilized the effectiveness of these local media, as it still uses other mass media more. Based on the findings, the researcher recommended that government should tilt away from using social media, television and other mass media, but pay more attention to the use of indigenous media, interpersonal, oral and radio, because of their effectiveness in rural communities, for adequate participation and sustainability of development, especially in the Southeast Nigeria.

Keywords: Media type Availability; Media type Usage; Development; Rural Communities; Southeast

INTRODUCTION

Community development is a legitimate process to foresee community advancement, improvement and instructive strategy to tackle social activity and development (Agboeze, Eze & Otu, 2001). It means that a medium of communication is essential for bringing desired transformation to the people, first before such people can contemplate change, as a necessary requirement for development. For people to participate in the development process, they need orientation, which comes through communication. Communication has become a key feature of sustainable development. There is an inseparable inter-connectivity between development communication and community development as they complement each other, to ensure a meaningful development. Agboeze, Eze and Otu (2001) posits that communication is imbedded in the heart of sustainable development. Development can be said to have occurred when society tends to be

industrialized, when there is significant increase in the production of goods and services, boost in the economic growth (Adelakun & Brikins, 2019). Development in this regard is hinged on economic growth or its improvement.

To deal with the development issues, the people require information and public enlightenment as a means of creating awareness and providing the necessary change. To facilitate decision making about the welfare of the people and how their lives can be improved through development, required for attitudinal and behavioral changes, the people also require a convincing evidence. Owuamalam (2016) agrees that unless the desire for change and for higher living standards take root in peasant communities, the introduction of new techniques from outside, signifying development, will hardly be accepted or fully exploited by the people. It shows that development communication must have peoples' expectation. That is to say, that before a new technology or idea is brought to the people, they must be communicated in the way that they can understand the gains of the project. Government also needs to be aware of people's feeling and what they are saying about its programmes and policies. In return, the government has the responsibility of reaching out to the people through the media (Chiakan & Tsafa, 2021).

Non participation of people in the development process in Nigeria, stems from lack of adequate and appropriate media. The assertion by Orange Knowledge Programme University (2022), the human development programs focuses on building human capabilities and not forgetting the potentiality of individuals, with people being at the centre of the development process, both politically, economically environmentally and socially. This perspective further believed that communication for development, if centered on the capacity of human development, will go a long way in helping to progressively elevate the quality of their living environment, improving living standard and using improved equipment with benefits from wider participation in development projects.

Media plays the role of facilitating and helping to share the information to appeal to the people, and bringing their attention to bear on the community development, thereby allowing them to take part, in the development activities. However, when media is not considered in reaching out to the members of the community for adequate participation, it becomes a huge challenge in achieving target of sustainable development projects.

Where there is no media, there is no development. Again, the primary purpose of media is communication. In turn, effective communication facilitates development. Meanwhile, effective communication is a pre-requisite of development, and this is achievable through language. In turn, media must be seen to be conveying the intended meaning as a means to achieving set goals, and not an end in itself (Kapur, 2018).

The set goals in this case, would be sustainable projects, such as electricity, portable water, healthcare, among other development projects that aim at improving the living standards of a particular rural community. Again, communication just like language, is not an end in itself, it is a vehicle to achieving set goals or attracting cooperation of a target participants for development in the Southeast region.

Most times, communicators have target objectives to be achieved. In the case of the South East Nigeria, these aspirations which include the development of religion through provisions of infrastructure, could be achieving sustainable development projects that will aid in standard of living of the people of the zone. Therefore, to solve the problems of under development due to lack of infrastructure and the unsustainable projects, there is need to identify the fact that to achieve rural development, community participation, from the stages of planning to realization of the projects, can be achieved through communication to the target people. This can be achieved if the appropriate media is used to reach to the people for participation.

With the above assertion, one can now believe that development projects can be achieved, if information and technology are shared effectively, and beneficiary or community are encouraged and committed to achieve desired success. To improve the living standard of the rural dwellers, there is need to involve them in the development process, through the use of appropriate communication strategy. Only with communication will the project beneficiaries become involved or become actors, for the success of the project. The success of communication depends on setting it apart as the core strategy in setting development priorities and carrying out planning, implementing and evaluating of programme, and also as a tool for training at all levels. Communication is an indispensable tool for development. Chiakaan and Ahmad (2014, p.2) observe that communication is the act of understanding that occur between the sender and the receiver through interaction

by both parties. They further stated that the understanding is the type based on achieving peace, unity and development to be attained in undeveloped society.

This is to say that unless beneficiaries, or the rural people who are the driving forces of their own development be at the centre of the development or involved in the planning, no amount of investment or provision of technology and inputs will bring about sustainability in their development.

This therefore brings the question of the particular mode of communication that will be most suitable, available, accessible, effective and preferable for achieving development projects in rural communities of the South East, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The provision of adequate infrastructure will help bring about socio-economic and political development of the people in the rural communities in Southeast Nigeria. By so doing, the living standard of the people will be improved. However, rural communities in Southeast Nigeria face significant development challenges, from non-availabilities of infrastructure to a good number of projects being unsustainable. A situation that keeps the rural dwellers in persistence lack. The government, as change agents and providers of these development projects, over the years have employed the use of community leaders, political leaders and the mass media only, to facilitate the provision of the projects for development. Despite the use of these community and political leaders, as well as media, the problem of non-availability and unsustainability of projects, continue to rear their ugly heads in the region. Non-availability of development projects and unsustainability of the existing ones bring about lack in the social, economic and political progress in these communities. This unavailability and lack of sustainability of project in the rural communities, in extension affects the Southeast Zone of Nigeria, bringing the Zone on the map of areas that failed in the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations. The government will also not achieve its target objective of promotion of social, economic and political progress of the people. This is because the target people who are beneficiaries of these projects, are not involved. The persistence in the lack of social, economic and political development can result to the people being cut off from reality, To solve this perennial problem, it becomes imperative that government should involve the people, conduct community scanning, a process of checking the actual needs of the people in an area before embarking on the provision of the project, or need assessment, to ascertain their needs and media channels to use to achieve sustainable project development.

Although there are other research on the significant of the study works on solving the problem of non-availability and unsustainability of community projects but they had dwelt only on the government use of mass media channels community and political leaders in solving the problems. This research work solved the problem of exploration of the potentiality of indigenous media and participatory communication approaches will have more significant impact in achieving sustainable development projects in rural communities of Southeast Nigeria. This research work has filled the gap of limitation in the exploration of indigenous media, face to face and oramedia, by government as change agents in achieving sustainable development projects in rural communities of Southeast Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The study sought to find out the types of media that is most available, accessible and can be used in communicating development of rural communities in Southeast geo political zone of Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. Identify the various development media availability among rural dwellers of Southeast Nigeria.
2. Ascertain the effectiveness of the media for the development purposes in the select communities.
3. Identify the challenges and barriers to the effective use of various media in the select communities.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Technological Determination and Participatory theories

Technological Determination Theory

Technological determination is the belief that technology is the principal initiator of the society's transformation. The emergence of this theory is usually attributed to the American sociologist Thorsten Veblen, who formulated the causal link between the technology and the society. According to the believers of technological determination, any social changes are driven by the technology, technology development,

communication technology and media. Technology influences the way human beings connect with the outside world in their day-to-day activities. The adoption of new technology can offer opportunities, it can also pose threats.

The application of technological determinism theory to this study, is apt as it is the theory that can take the form of an idea, theory or a way of explaining technology development in history or the present, but can also take the form of actual material structures that implicitly or explicitly permeate and influence the society of Southeast Nigeria. Technological determinism is a natural result of design being a balance between what is societally desirable and technically possible. At the instance of technological improvement in media and information communications, the media have been transformed and shaped severally over time. The transformations that have taken place have in turn re-shaped people's understanding and definitions of media effects or influence.

Participatory Theory

Participatory theory believe that meaningful development can only be achieved when the target group is fully involved from the inception to the post-implementation stage of the development process. The theory which was propounded by Paulo Freire in 1970 is one of the paradigms of development that have evolved over time. Proponent of this theory was either informed by history, experiences, orientations or other related factors. The participatory school of thought encourages the use of the mass media, interpersonal communication and traditional media to mobilize and sensitize the people and communities to play an active role in identifying their problems, prioritizing their needs, conceptualizing remedial projects and applying the change or development options as key players in the development process.

This participatory theory prefers two-way communication to the top to down process. That is to say, instead of talking at or talking to the people, the theory encourages talking with the people. This entails that dialogue and purposeful participation of the people of the Southeast are crucial elements in the successful implementation of social programmes. Alegu and Maku (2020) cited in Okunna that the participation of beneficiaries in the development process should not only involve sending feedback concerning the project, but should equally involve taking part in discussion and decision-making. That is to say, meetings between government as change agents and the beneficiaries should not be an avenue to inform them about the plans or decision that have been already taken, but should be a forum of interaction to give them the opportunity to contribute or air their views and collectively take decisions on the proposed projects. The theory best suits this research as it tends to bring the variables to the knowledge of the people involved in the projects. Talking about participation, the theory x-rayed how imperative the involvement of beneficiaries are to the sustainability of the projects. Suffice it to say that, no matter how technically advanced the media may be, the messages skillfully packaged, and the information very relevant, scholars believe that they are not enough to bring about meaningful and sustainable results except the beneficiaries are part of the process.

Media and Development

Media is one of the medium of communications that have brought the world into one single unit. As the word media derives from the Latin medium that means in the middle. The media refers to traditional mass communication system and content generators as well as other technologies for mediated human speech. The Media play significant role in development communication which is disseminated through knowledge, discussion forum, teaching ideas, skill acquisition and consensus stability, for the state. The digital media and information sharing provides opportunity for most members of the community, both literate and illiterates to participate in information sharing. Digital community started two thousand years ago and has continued to evolve. Machado (2022) opined that individuals are now increasingly connected, geographically, and the wide gap is thinning due to digital communication and web 2.0 tools. This Onyejelem, Ude-Akpeh and Uduma (2015) collaborated, that since the evolution of digital communication, new technologies have been changing communication into the context of the knowledge society. The use of development communication in broadcasting, in promoting development was analyzed by Shaibu (2016) where he noted that, in order to improve holistically the growth of education, health, environment and other sectors of the economy, it becomes imperative to employ broadcast programmes that encourage growth and development, rather than political driven programmes.

In understanding deeply the concept of development in terms of communication and sustainability, it becomes imperative to note the importance of sustainable development in underdeveloped countries as captured by Phuong and Adamkolo (2020). The issues of media ownership, concentration, sensationality and commercialization on development communication in Nigeria, are some of the elements that hinder efforts to disseminate information for development, in addition to the issue with media access, plurality of opinions and divergence of views, all being compromised as well as the problem of lack of participatory development communication. Baruwa, Beatriz, Joao, Ronald, Erik and Antomoic (2021), argues that though some TV stations' use of animated programs to promote development communication, educational and informational program require more attention.

There is also need for community radio programmes that create awareness and enlightenment campaign geared towards inspiring public in support of food security. There is considerable link between food security and media in development (Dennis, Chukwu, Okoronkwo & Enyinnaya, 2020). Also Babatunde (2018) examined the issue of the nationwide strike in 2012 in Nigeria by the Nigeria Labour Congress (NLC) against the removal of fuel subsidy. It was recorded as being successful due to the use of media, as an effective tool for mobilizing majority of people, with the messages of development. The media served as the watchdog, holding the government accountable and enabling their active participation in the development of the society.

Media also promote sports development, where government and private investors are advised to invest massively in sport development initiative, which bring development at the grassroots. Oyedokun (2021) looked at how media affects sports the value of television and radio as veritable platforms for sports communication and development in Nigeria. Thus, media refers various means of communication, its aim to reach a very large population, such as the entire population of country.

Development Communication Process

To carry out any development programme, it requires the development communication or change agent to be well equipped and acquainted with the target audience, beneficiaries or community, their development needs, as well as belief, language, religion, culture, their level of education and general occupation, this cited in Ristic, Mihilovic, Ckerevac, Okrmac and Salketic, Mayen, Johnson and Babatunde (2020) believe that, such information could only be gotten through conducting a research or a baseline survey.

According to the authors, the baseline survey assist in the establishment of the prior position or belief of the target evidence and then the expected outcome, and this invariably helps the development communication in choosing the appropriate media or channels of communication, as well as the message type(s) that would meet the needs and beliefs of the target people.

It is usually a common phenomenon for the government at any levels, as well as non-governmental organizations to equip themselves of the information about the target beneficiary, and then convey their messages through the representatives, or community leaders. This can be achieved by the use of town hall meeting or through other media of communication available and accessible to the people, in other to enlighten them on the proposed project, thereby seeking their participation. This approach has over time proven to be most effective in mobilizing the beneficiaries, to participate in development projects aimed at improving their wellbeing.

The process of development from inception or planning stage, down to the implementation stages of any project requires a set of communication activities. These activities which are acknowledged by various authors are:

- i. Identification of problem, which is very crucial in planning stage.
- ii. Research – this takes care of information gathering about the target beneficiaries, to ascertain both their geographical, belief, culture, language and educational qualifications.
- iii. Message structure and form of dissemination,
- iv. Choice of media channels of communication that is available and accessible to the people. The choice of appropriate channels, according to Carr (2017) is very vital to the success of any change programme.

- v. Awareness campaign and sensitization in other to mobilize people for participation. Relevant information in considered in creating awareness to the people,
- vi. Advocacy – UNICEF (2015) defines advocacy as the deliberate process, which is based on evidence, to directly or indirectly influence the decision making of stakeholders and other relevant authorities, in other to support and carryout action.
- vii. The involvement of recipients
- viii. Project execution which is the climax of the whole process, where mobilization of all resources geared towards the implementation and actualization of the goals of the projects.
- ix. Finally, evaluation where the project is appraised. The measurement of the project from the planning stage, to actualization. The process of development communication are cited by Okunna (2002) in Inyang, Alegu, Iorlaha, Adelaja & Maka (2019).

Rural and Community Development in Southeast Nigeria

In Nigeria over the years, policy makers and development experts have pronounced the stated objectives and strategies that derive development of rural and community. However, despite that there are still existing gap between formulating policy and implementation which bring to the fore, the reality of the level of the development of the rural people. For example to solve these problem many approaches have been employed, in terms of rural development planning and execution. States, local government, mobilization of the rural dwellers for participation, have been employed as strategies for community development project implementation. The majority of Nigerian population is said to reside in the rural communities, and despite this phenomenon, rural development has persistently eluded rural areas across the nation. In contrary, rural development has continued to serve as a tool for sustainable development in Nigeria (Asaju & Ayeni, 2021). To further stem the surge in the rural-urban migration, it becomes imperative to examine the effort of bringing development to the rural areas. For example, a look at the National Development Plans of ten years, of from 1975-1985, and other rural development strategies, such as Operation Feed the Nation (OFN), the Green Revolution Programme, River Basin Development Authorities, as well as the Agricultural Development Projects, all emphasizing the need to solve the problem of rural-development.

The government also realizes the importance of brining the underdeveloped and neglected rural areas, among the mainstream of development in the National Area (Egbe, 2016).

Media of Communication for Development

The problem of appropriate choice of media for rural development should be a discourse in its social context and it is also believed that there is no generally valid blueprint available for a particular media for carrying development messages. Traditional media as well as modern media of communication are also available, which is dependent on the situation, the purpose and their availability within the locality.

Traditional Media Channels: Relevance in Community Development

Traditional media have been in existence in Nigerian traditional societies for long and have been used as medium of communication especially in the rural parts of the country where the modern media of communication has either less penetration or no access of modern media at all. Despite the revolution of modern media which brought about innovations such as internet, social networking and other forms of new media; the traditional media still occupy some salient space in the delivery of message to a large number of people in a given society.

Various scholars have employed different terms in defining, explaining and referring to traditional media such as – Local media, folk media, Oramedia described by Ugbojah as cited in Chukwu and Anorue, (2019) as well as informal media, and indigene media, described by Akpabio cited in Chukwu and Anorue (2019).

Traditional media channels as according to Ansu-Kyeremah, cited in Chukwu and Anorue (2019), are any form of communication system which as a result of its origin, form and integration into a particular culture, helps as a channels for disseminating messages in a way to gain values, institution and symbolism of the cultural values through its unique qualities and attributes. Similarly, Ukonu and Wogu, as cited in Chukwu and Anorue (2019) defined the traditional system of communication as the modes of exchanging meaning, which are rooted in a people's culture, for the area of low education to pre-modernized individual.

One feature that is significant in the definition of traditional media is the culture and as an inference to the ways of living by the people of a particular community (Akpabio cited in Chukwu & Anorue, 2019). According to Akpabio, the principles of all definition of traditional media, is an indication that it is part and parcel of the way of life of people. Traditional communication systems which is also known as indigenous communication systems, make use of folk that is embedded in the culture of the people. It denotes that channels are embedded within the traditional more of a people and contributing significantly to their history and culture. Ekwelie and Okonkwo cited in Chukwu and Anorue (2019) opined that traditional media are rooted in the peoples culture and has remained significantly valid to the people as channels for facilitating the exchange of ideas, values, even with urbanization and migration to urban cities.

For ages, rural population living in interior villages without access to modern means of communication have relied on words of the mouth and traditional forms of communication as a means of sharing knowledge and information, as well as providing entertainment. Traditional communication systems refer to every organized processes of production and exchange of information that are managed by rural communities. Some of traditional channels of communication include traditional theatre, masks and puppets performances, tales, proverbs, riddles, masquerading, drum and gong languages, and traditional songs. These traditional channels of communication should be seen as a cultural and indigenous response to different community needs, geared towards information, education social protest and entertainment. These systems are often used to solve the problem of persuading the people for the need for change, or for development of a rural community and need for the preservation of cultural values.

The rate of illiteracy among the rural dwellers are mostly high, as well as high rate of poverty that is added to the inadequacy of the mass media to reach about 700million people residing in remote areas. The mass media to them, proved to be sophisticated, impersonal and unbelievable as compared to the traditional performances that are familiar to them, as the villagers could not only see and hear, but can also touch. By this, all communication processes based on media that are not initiated and managed by the rural dwellers themselves, such as radio, video, newspapers, television as well as the new media will not be perceived as traditional and are considered foreign or external to the rural community.

Communication is a product of culture, as culture determine the code structure, meaning and context of the communication that takes place. The high rate of participation of rural agents in the production and use of traditional media high premium given to traditional values, symbols and realities and at the same time, ensure that such media preference appeal to rural audiences. For illiterate rural dwellers, occasions for exchange of information have been in local festivities, family gatherings, traditional and religious associations, interaction with itinerary merchants and encounters at market places or water well. This means, allows the younger people in the community to share their needs in the midst of the whole community through an existing and culturally accepted channel of communication.

African society has different traditional ways of disseminating information through recognized official means like signs, sounds, and symbols. Manan, Ahmad and Hasan (2017) defined development as a progress of the individual well-being and the improvement of the quality of the life of the people. Communication is so vital to human existence just like the oxygen is essential to human life, because it helps to sustain the human society. The process of communicating with people have changed with the advent of traditional media. Traditional media is also known as user-generated media. It educates and inform people about any development in a novel way and bring about a platform of two-way communication (Banerjee, 2015).

The traditional media are defined as ‘those media which attempt to send a message to a particular set of targeted audience group in a given time in local dialect with entertainment (Mathiyazhagan, Kaur, Ravindhar & Devrani, 2015). Communication can also be referred to as a social interactive tool, since it helps to promote collective actions and other social behaviors that make life meaningful and interesting for human existence, and because of its importance no society can progress or survive without communication process. One cannot quantify the magnitude of tradio-media communication symbols. This is because they are borne out of the popular instrument of reality that make up the locality (Obiagwu, 2017). Message is very important in communication because the act of passing messages is communication itself. Everything we do with our body or with other medium such as the thoughts in our mind and the words we use for those thoughts, the sounds we make, our gestures, our facial expressions and perhaps even our touch or smell all

communicate information, this tells us how effective communication can be, it involves our every seconds' action, therefore, there is no communication without a message being passed across. Communication comes in different forms which include the intrapersonal, interpersonal, group, public, mass communication etc. All these are different ways through which we interact, associate, communicate, relate, share ideas, views, opinion, information, norms and values with ourselves and others. In communication, channels mean the medium or means through which communication is being passed or disseminated (Esimokha, as cited in Inole-Abu, 2018). Because it is communication with a social conscience, development communication is oriented towards human beings, that is, towards the human aspect of development. Even though it is primarily associated with rural development, it is nevertheless also concerned with urban problems.

Nigeria is regarded as multi-channel communicator due to the different channels through which communication is being disseminated in both urban and rural settings which help to proffer a better result of what is being sent. It is successful and effective in reaching rural people because they emanate from the local culture and tradition of the people and they use familiar channel, the local language, pass relevant messages, address local issues, needs and problem and use local resources for development of the society. They are seen as the vehicle the common people employ for the delivery of their messages. Folk media are some of the most vibrant representation of traditional media because they reflect communication channel for, by and of the common people of a society or region (Reich & Godler, 2017).

In rural areas and developing nations, folk media represents the masses of people most deprived of specific messages. Thus, folk media cover a wide range of traditional communication channels, including storytelling, street theatre, puppetry, song and dance, market place, Town-Crier amongst others. Folk media are also representatives of a traditional way of life based on customs, beliefs and art that makes up a distinctive culture. It draws upon people's past, present and future, providing them with glimpse of reality that result in education and entertainment. However, African communities lay emphasis on events rather than date. These events and probably the date, formed part of their culture (Scannell, 2017). The meeting of two cultures often leads to cultural shock or what the scholars termed "clash of cultures". African communication scholars put more emphasis on the study of the modern media of communication which includes the radio, television, internet, and billboard, but due to lack of development most of the rural dwellers are not familiar with these modern media ways of communication.

Transformation and Development of Traditional Media in the Era of New Media

With the speed in development and the popularity of internet technology, the forms of new media based on digital technology, wireless and satellite communication and other means of technical communication tend to develop rapidly and widely (Cao, 2017). With the advantages of high openness, wide coverage as well as the advantage of increase in efficiency, in internet technology which the new media has, it has continued to occupy more discourse power, influence and guiding principle in the field of information communication, thus the field of information communication finds its way to the era of new media (Jin, 2018).

In the new media era, on the one hand, it's efficiency of the screen, analysis, mines and predictions in massive information geared toward improving the innovation and content accuracy. Invariably, it uses words, pictures, audio, video which helps to process visual and audible content, to know the interesting and efficiently realize the forms of communication. The new media also interact with the audience in the process of super-imposing information communication, which positively leads to the growth of the new media influence. According to Liang, Pan, Huang, Ling, Huang and Li (2016), in this context, the traditional should tackle their own challenging and shortcomings and borrow a leaf from the advantages of new media elements, in other to gain their own transformation and development.

Meanwhile, the analysis of the value or importance of the transformation and how traditional media have developed in the area of the new media, becomes helpful in other to give clarity to the direction and objective of the transformation of traditional media, as well as exploring the practical way of the transformation of traditional media.

The analysis of the report, from the three dimension of allocation of resource, dissemination of information mode, as well as the ability to guide public opinion, and explore the characteristics of traditional media reshaping competitiveness, expanding influence and the ability to strengthen appeal through transformation,

which regarded as a value connotation of traditional media transformation and development in the era of new media (Nan, 2020). Optimization of the allocation of the resources of the traditional media, as well as reshaping its competitiveness, forms the primary value of the transformation and development of traditional media in the era of new media. Neng (2018) asserts that traditional media can optimize its own resources values through transformation taking from the perspective of practical operations. Form him, there is need for firstly that transforming and development can facilitate the optimization of the talent characteristic of traditional media, highlight the introduction of young teams with the new technology, new idea, new objectives, new vision and new abilities, in other to provide necessary support for the sustainable development of traditional media. Traditional media can also build new traffic channels, which will connect customers, superimpose its own advantages of offline, and can as well realize its own synchronization collaboration development of its own online and offline, and will finally fully show its own content advantages. According to Wu (2018) traditional media can integrate its own media technology resources, bring to limelight the research, as well as application of media technology and enhance the ability of its resources, ability of its technology and ultimately improve their core competitiveness, based on the transformation and development of traditional media.

Changing the Mode of Information Dissemination, Expanding Traditional Media Influence

The core value of the transformation and the development of traditional media in the era of the new media, is to change the mode of transmitting information by the traditional media and to also increase the influence of traditional media (Wang, 2021). Wang believes that the internet has influenced greatly on the way human live, even in the field of information dissemination. In the era of new media, the mode of transmitting information is what Wang believes, is too rigid, that it does not only lack enough attractive content information, but also slightly appear dull and boring in form. Yuan (2016) collaborated by asserting that this mode of transmitting information by traditional media, in this era of new media, is difficult to attract young clients and meet the needs of the market. Yuan believes that, at the same time, the direction of disseminating information by traditional media, is usually one-way and this method lack communication and interaction between the sender of information or information transmitter and the receiver or audience. This however, according to Yuan (2021) reduces the influence and attraction of traditional media itself. The traditional media through the transformation and development, will be saddled with the roles, contents and modes of new media, will also learn from their experience and mode, Yuan, recommends that traditional media will innovate their own information dissemination mode and thereby expand their influence.

METHOD OF STUDY

This mixed research methods were employed to ascertain the media channels availability and use in the development of South-East rural areas. Survey method helped the researcher to get data from the beneficiaries of projects, while indepth interview gave the researcher the opportunity to get responses from the benefactor or the change agent. The area of study for this work is the South-East Geo Political Zone of Nigeria. Southeast Nigeria has five States namely; Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo States. The researcher selected only three states out of the five states. The states selected for the study are: Anambra, Ebonyi and Enugu States. Anambra State has three Senatorial Districts, with 21 Local Government Areas. Ebonyi State also has three Senatorial Districts and 13 Local Government Areas while Enugu State with three Senatorial Districts, consists of 17 Local Government Areas. The population of the study is Five hundred and forty six thousand, nine hundred and six (546,906) respondents. This population is made up of the sum total population of the 18 communities selected for the study according to National Population Commission 2023. For indepth interview three communities and nine local government chairmen were selected for interviews. One local government chairman was selected from the study areas in each of the three states, while commissions for information were selected from the three select states. For government officials indepth interview was conducted for answers, the responses to the questions were analysed thematically using the explanation building technique.

Selected senatorial districts, local government areas, communities of study and their populations.

Senatorial District	L.G.A	Community	Population of communities
Anambra Central	Dunukofa L.G.A	Ukwulu	19,642
		Nawgu	18,520
Anambra North	AyamelumL.G.A	Anaku	9,090
		Omor	34,047
Anambra South	Nnewi South L.G.A	Ekwulumili	52,000
		Osumenyi	95,238
Enugu West	Oji-River L.G.A	Inyi	38,278
		Akpugoeze	9,570
Enugu East	Nkanu West L.G.A	Akpugo	56,400
		Obuofia	14,100
Enugu North	UdenuL.G.A	Obollo-afor	20,100
		Obollo-Etiti	18,321
Ebonyi Central	OhozaraL.G.A	OkposiAchara	22,612
		MgbomOkposi	20,100
Ebonyi North	AbakalikiL.G.A	Abakpa	15,928
		Amagu	47,786
Ebonyi South	Ezza South L.G.A	Onueka	36,084
		Amudo	19,090
Total POP			546,906

Source 2023 census.gov.ng

The sample size for this study is 384 as according to Krejcie and Morgan (1970) for population ranging from 10 to 1,000,000 at 95 percent confidence level and using the formula for calculating sample size recommended in Krejcie and Morgan (1970). Multi-stage sampling technique was employed in this study as follows:

Stage I – Selection of States

The researcher employed probability random sampling technique, to select the three states from the South East Zones.

Stage II – Selection of Senatorial District

The researcher selected the entire three senatorial districts of the selected states, making it nine senatorial districts selected.

Stage III – Selection of Local Governments

At this stage of local Government, the researcher selected one local government area each from the nine senatorial districts, making it nine local government areas selected for the study. Meanwhile, this was done using purposive sampling techniques based on their characteristics and level of underdevelopment.

Stage IV – Selection of Communities

The communities chosen at this stage was done purposively. The researcher chose two communities each out of the nine local government areas selected. That is, in each one local government, two communities were selected. This made it a total of eighteen communities studied, hence forming the population of the study.

This study made use of the questionnaire and in-depth interview guide for the collection of data. The questionnaire was designed in such a way that it elicited the required information that helped the researcher to provide answers to the research questions posed for the study. The questionnaire was divided into two sections to cover the demographic and thematic data of the respondents. The demographic questions exposed the researcher to the personal details of the respondents such as age, sex, level of education and designation in community. On the other hand, the thematic data contained both open ended and close ended question items which helped the researcher to get the appropriate information that provided answers to the research

questions on the respondents' views about the media of communication and government usage in communities studied.

The indepth interviews also helped the researcher get information from the government as a stakeholder in the most available, accessible and effective media of communication and usage in getting people to participate in development projects. Five indepth interviews with follow up questions were designed to get information from the commissioners and local government chairmen.

The test-retest method was applied for the study to ensure reliability of instrument. The data were collected for this research and coded with respect to the different variables of the study to ease the process of data entry and data interpretation. The responses from the interviewee were transcribed using edited transcription method to collect data. The study used descriptive and inferential method of data analysis. Coding of the data was done according to different variables and descriptive statistics. The results were further presented using tables and charts.

FINDINGS

This study utilized both the quantitative and qualitative research designs. The findings include the following: The study revealed that the most available source where the respondents get information about development of their area, is the face-to-face and traditional newsmen or town criers, with radio coming third in the percentage list. The study however found that other media channels like television, newspaper, magazine and internet, though have the capacity to reach to a large number of audience or people, but are not considered available sources in these communities studied.

The study also found that language is very powerful in mobilizing people for development, as participation is high when the media channels utilize indigenous language.

The study further found that factors such as high cost of accessing channel, low income, and poor educational background, militate against their use of media channels of their choice.

Again, the study found that the use of traditional media through face-to-face interaction and traditional newsmen, will enable change agents overcome problems associated with participation, which is one of the major handicaps in the use of other mass media in disseminating development messages.

Lastly, it was revealed that the government used some indigenous media, the community leaders, political leaders, radio, masquerade, age grade; but the government did not fully utilize the indigenous means of communication, oramedia and radio there was limited exploration of the potential of indigenous or community media, as well as engaging the people.

Conclusion

Although all forms of communication have unique characteristics and roles which they play in achieving sustainable development, but indigenous media and oral communication are found to be more effective in getting to the rural dwellers to participate in development purposes and for achieving sustainability. The government should also use these modes of communication which are found to be effective in reaching to the people and getting immediate feedback. Indigenous media is one of the key means through which access to and application of knowledge and information are facilitated to the rural communities. The use of traditional media provide development agents with the support they need, as well as serve as an enhancing tool for the achievement of development purposes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study and conclusion drawn, the following recommendations were made to address the issue of non-participation of rural dwellers to the planning, and execution of development projects, due to the nonuse of available, accessible and effective media of communication, among rural dwellers of south east Nigeria.

There is need for managers and operators of rural development projects to ascertain the available traditional communication methods in their target areas of operations, with a view to integrating the relevant traditional communication modes into their efforts at disseminating development messages to rural dwellers.

There is need for community scanning or need assessment at the onset, in order to ascertain both the project need of the people, and the best media approach, as well as the language to be used. This will help for participation and sustainability, as the finding from this study showed that most unsustainable projects in most

rural communities, are as a result of non-participation of the rural dwellers, who are usually not included from the planning stage.

There is need for the dissemination of the right information gotten from data and should be used to get to the people, to participate and help sustain development projects in their areas.

There is need for sufficient attention to the usage of all the indigenous media of communication, face to face and radio in achieving development projects in the Southeast Nigeria.

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